

LIVED EXPERIENCE ON THE HYBRID LEARNING MODALITY OF TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 3

Pages: 456-470

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2360

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13771944

Manuscript Accepted: 07-29-2024

Lived Experience on the Hybrid Learning Modality of Tanauan City College: A Phenomenological Study

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the experiences of students and faculty at Tanauan City College (TCC) with the Hybrid Learning Modality (HLM). The objectives are to identify specific challenges faced by both groups, assess the impact on academic outcomes and engagement, and gather recommendations to enhance the hybrid learning experience at TCC. A qualitative phenomenological approach was employed to capture the lived experiences of participants. In-depth interviews were conducted with seven faculty members and seven students. The data were transcribed and analyzed thematically to identify common themes and insights. The findings reveal that faculty members initially faced difficulties adapting to HLM but eventually embraced flexible teaching methods, leading to improved student engagement and satisfaction. Challenges included resource constraints, technological limitations, and time management issues. Students appreciated the flexibility and convenience of online learning but struggled with technical connectivity and limited interaction. Adaptive strategies included improved time management and adjusting to new learning environments. Participants recommended better infrastructure, continuous professional development for faculty, and enhanced engagement strategies. This study provides valuable insights into improving hybrid learning at TCC, highlighting the importance of flexibility, resource availability, and continuous improvement. The findings aim to inform policy and practice, fostering a more inclusive, effective, and engaging educational experience for all stakeholders at Tanauan City College.

Keywords: *adaptive strategies, faculty experiences, Hybrid Learning Modality, student experiences*

Introduction

The educational landscape in the Philippines has witnessed a significant transformation in recent years, driven by both global trends and local adaptations. One of the most notable changes is the rapid integration of hybrid learning modalities, which blend traditional face-to-face instruction with online components. This shift is exemplified by the Hybrid Learning Modality of Tanauan City College, offering a unique lens through which the challenges and opportunities of education can be examined in a local context. TCC has adopted the hybrid modality not only in response to evolving educational needs but also due to the lack of available classrooms to accommodate all students in a purely in-person setup.

In response to evolving educational needs, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) issued Memorandum Order No. 16 on November 11, 2022. This order directed the return to in-person learning while allowing HEIs the flexibility to design and deliver their degree programs through onsite or hybrid learning modalities starting the second semester of the 2022-2023 school year. CHED Chairperson Prospero de Vera III emphasized that this order aims to provide clarity and support to HEIs, facilitating their progressive transition to on-site learning within the broader framework of flexible learning. HEIs are required to conduct comprehensive assessments of institutional capabilities, analyze learner needs and preferences, and consult stakeholders to decide the appropriate delivery method for their programs (Ciriaco, 2022).

Hybrid Learning Modality offers powerful results by combining online and onsite educational contexts. The use of hybrid learning in educational settings ought to be promoted for this reason, and the requisite equipment and resources ought to be made available (Kazu & Yalçın, 2022). Furthermore, Çırak Kurt et al. (2018) noted that while some activities and practices should continue outside of the classroom, face-to-face lessons are taught alongside in-class activities in the hybrid learning process. There is a need for an auxiliary tool that can manage the distance education process in order to carry out these practices outside of the classroom in an acceptable manner.

Similarly, with hybrid learning, each student has a more individualized learning experience that is tailored to their specific needs. This is accomplished by combining online and offline training. Students who study best in a traditional classroom setting, for example, can profit from face-to-face connection with their peers and teachers, while others who prefer a more autonomous learning style, can profit from the flexibility and autonomy that online learning offers. By offering a learning environment that is customized to each student's needs, hybrid learning can ultimately aid in the success of all students (Goel, 2022). In a study conducted by Alsalhi et al. (2021), it was found that hybrid learning helps students achieve academically by ensuring that they have a thorough comprehension of the course material covered. These outcomes could be linked to a blended learning application's beneficial aspects in the teaching process, such as its adaptability, promotion of students' efficiency, fulfilling of students' needs, development of engagement, and taking considerations individual differences between students.

On one hand, in a hybrid learning environment, there are a variety of difficulties that both teachers and students must overcome. The need for instructors to drastically alter their teaching method posed one difficulty. For both in-person and online students, they must

be able to offer a comparable high-quality educational experience (Raes et al., 2019). Similarly, According to Mayer (2023), there is a divergence in perspectives between students and educators regarding hybrid education. While students appreciate the flexibility afforded by blended learning, educators primarily perceive it as complex, with fewer apparent advantages. Consequently, educational institutions and technology providers involved in hybrid education should consider both students' and educators' viewpoints when designing hybrid learning environments.

On the other hand, while the academics demonstrate a high degree of readiness in addressing technical issues, some students in their hybrid classes exhibit lower levels of motivation, engagement, and interaction compared to those in their traditional in-person classes. There are some difficulties associated with hybrid learning and teaching, including the increased workload for class preparation, the management of both in-person and online classes, the unfamiliarity with designing interactive teaching methods for both settings, and the challenges in effectively monitoring online students' progress (Li et al., 2023).

Moreover, Singh et al. (2021) noted that in order to offer students meaningful and captivating learning opportunities, educators and academic leaders must prioritize the development of suitable infrastructure for hybrid and blended learning approaches. A key emphasis should be placed on enhancing the capabilities of faculty members, enabling them to become more proficient in online teaching techniques, e-Learning tools, and the incorporation of innovative technology to enhance the teaching and learning process.

Hence, it is crucial to underscore that the difficulties universities encounter when introducing the hybrid approach to professional training can be mitigated to maintain and enhance educational excellence, meeting the evolving requirements of today's students. Additionally, ensuring that the teaching staff receives effective ongoing training to bolster their digital competencies is imperative. This will enable them to effectively implement the plans and strategies developed to achieve the objectives established by the administrative management of both public and private universities (Suarez et al., 2020).

As cited by Utami (2018), hybrid learning modality promotes active student engagement, enabling them to take control of their learning pace and prepare for class in advance. This approach supports student-centered learning and aligns with the principles of 21st-century education. The current study not only addresses the challenge of balancing online and in-person learning but also underscores the importance of delivering high-quality content. Furthermore, hybrid learning equips educators with the flexibility to offer diverse formats of learning materials.

This research endeavor aims to delve into the lived experiences of students and faculty members at Tanauan City College, shedding light on their encounters, challenges, and triumphs within the context of hybrid learning by examining their perceptions, preferences, and recommendations. In doing so, it endeavors to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on the evolution of education in the digital age and offer practical insights that can enrich the hybrid learning experience for all stakeholders involved. As the researchers embark on the journey to explore the lived experiences of Tanauan City College's students and faculty members in the realm of hybrid learning, they aspire to create a more inclusive, engaging, and effective educational environment that aligns with the evolving needs of the educational community.

The current educational scenario presents several challenges that necessitate this study. The sudden shift to hybrid learning modalities has led to significant disruptions, with both faculty and students grappling with technological, pedagogical, and logistical issues. This study is crucial in identifying these challenges and providing actionable insights to improve the hybrid learning experience. The uniqueness of this study lies in its focus on a specific local context, which has been underrepresented in existing literature. By addressing the specific needs and experiences of TCC's stakeholders, this research aims to contribute to a more tailored and effective implementation of hybrid learning in similar educational settings.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the lived experiences of students and teachers on the hybrid learning modality of Tanauan City College. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. Examine the lived experiences of students and faculty members in the hybrid learning modality of Tanauan City College.
2. Identify the specific challenges that students and faculty members encounter within the hybrid learning environment.
3. Analyze how teachers and students perceive these challenges affecting their academic outcomes and influencing teaching and student engagement.
4. Investigate the strategies and mechanisms that faculty members and students employ to adapt and succeed in the hybrid learning modality in response to the identified challenges.
5. Gather insights and recommendations from students and faculty members for enhancing the effectiveness of the hybrid learning modality at Tanauan City College.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design to capture the lived experiences of students and faculty members with the Hybrid Learning Modality (HLM) at Tanauan City College (TCC).

Participants

The study involved 14 participants in total, comprising seven faculty members and seven students from TCC. These participants were selected to provide diverse perspectives on the hybrid learning experience. Participants were selected based on a rigorous set of criteria to ensure relevant and current experiences. Faculty members were required to be actively teaching at least one hybrid course at Tanauan City College during the current semester. Similarly, students needed to be enrolled in at least one hybrid course at TCC for the current semester. This ensured that all participants had direct and recent experience with both the online and face-to-face components of the hybrid learning modality. Additionally, participants had to express a willingness to participate and provide informed consent, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose and their role in it.

Exclusion criteria were also strictly applied to maintain the study's focus. Faculty and students who had only participated in purely online or purely face-to-face learning were excluded, as their experiences would not align with the hybrid learning modality being studied. Participants who were unavailable for interviews or who declined to provide consent were also excluded. Furthermore, individuals who did not complete the interview process were not included in the final analysis, ensuring that all data collected were comprehensive and relevant to the study's objectives.

Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection was in-depth, semi-structured interviews. The interview guide included questions designed to explore participants' experiences, challenges, perceptions, and adaptive strategies related to the hybrid learning modality.

Procedure

Data were collected through face-to-face and virtual interviews, each lasting between 30 to 60 minutes. Interviews were recorded with participants' consent and subsequently transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the transcribed data. This involved coding the data to identify significant themes and patterns that reflect the participants' experiences and perceptions. The process included familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, and defining and naming themes.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection of participants' rights and well-being. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study by assigning pseudonyms to participants and securely storing all data.

Results and Discussion

After a thorough review of the data gathered, several themes were identified for the lived experiences of faculty members, such as adaptation and flexibility, student engagement and participation, overcoming challenges, and positive outcomes and satisfaction. Resource constraints, technological limitations, and time management and curriculum coverage are the challenges encountered by faculty members in a hybrid learning environment. Furthermore, perceptions of instructional effectiveness in the hybrid learning modality among faculty members include pedagogical adaptation and efficacy, overcoming technological barriers, and facilitating interactive learning experiences.

Additionally, the strategies and mechanisms that faculty members employ to adapt and succeed in the hybrid learning modality are the need for training and seminars, adaptation and skill development, sharing knowledge and collaboration, and enhancing student engagement through technology. Faculty members' insights and recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of the hybrid learning modality at Tanauan City College are accessibility and infrastructure, continuous professional development, blended learning approaches, and effective use and improvement of the LMS.

Moreover, flexibility and convenience, challenges of online learning, enhanced learning and personal growth, and support for working and non-traditional students were the themes identified for the lived experiences of students in the hybrid learning modality of Tanauan City College. Specific challenges encountered were technical issues and connectivity problems, limited interaction and engagement, and adaptation to hybrid learning. In contrast, the aspects of the hybrid learning modality that the students find most engaging are flexibility and time management, preference for face-to-face learning, and independent learning and habit formation. Further, the strategies and mechanisms that students employ to adapt and succeed in the hybrid learning modality are flexibility and time management, accessibility and convenience, adaptation to changing learning environments, and satisfaction and personal growth.

Finally, the students' insights and recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of the hybrid learning modality at Tanauan City College are enhancing student engagement and interaction, addressing students' socio-economic status, maintaining and improving the quality of teaching, and providing adequate time for learning.

Lived Experiences of the Faculty Members on the Hybrid Learning Modality

Theme 1: Adaptation and Flexibility

Educators initially perceived hybrid learning as challenging due to constraints such as limited time, students' gadget and internet availability, and environmental factors. However, they successfully adapted by becoming more flexible in lesson planning and delivery. This flexibility led to the development of improved teaching methods and resources tailored to both online and face-to-face settings.

Initially, expected difficulties due to logistical constraints but found that the hybrid modality allowed students to perform well and manage their work effectively. The statement underscores the unexpected benefits, such as reduced costs, which contributed to a positive teaching experience.

Faculty 1 stated that, "My experience with teaching in hybrid learning modality is quite an eye opener for me... I am satisfied with the performance of the students... I believe this learning modality is also helpful for everyone because of the reduced expenses for all."

The need for consistency in teaching across different modalities, highlighting the importance of flexible lesson planning to ensure seamless learning experiences. The acknowledgment of cost savings for students illustrates a significant advantage of hybrid learning, which can alleviate financial burdens.

Faculty 2 said that, "Hybrid learning modality at Tanauan City College teaches me to be a flexible educator... I always make sure that the students receive a consistent learning experience whether it is in person or online... Some students also tell me that because of this hybrid modality, they can save money, as well as they are given enough time to accomplish all activities that are assigned to them."

The effectiveness of hybrid learning enables the creation of more engaging and effective virtual resources. It can enhance the quality of instruction by integrating diverse and interactive materials, benefiting the learning process.

As the Faculty 4 highlighted that, "I might characterize my experience as a teacher at Tanauan City College using the hybrid learning mode as a more effective method of instruction... provide additional, more effective, and engaging virtual learning resources for my pupils."

There is an initial difficulty of adapting to hybrid learning but ultimately it is preferred over traditional methods. This indicates that despite the challenges, the hybrid modality offers advantages that make it a favorable teaching approach in the long run.

Faculty 5 noted that, "Hard at first but challenging. But I like it more than the traditional way of teaching."

The challenges and subsequent adaptation identified by faculty members resonate with findings from Alsalhi et al. (2021), who highlighted the adaptability and efficiency promoted by hybrid learning. Similarly, Raes et al. (2019) and Mayer (2023) underscored the need for educators to modify their teaching methods and address challenges in providing consistent, high-quality education in both online and face-to-face settings. These findings reinforce the importance of flexibility and innovation in navigating the complexities of hybrid learning environments.

Theme 2: Student Engagement and Participation

The hybrid learning modality resulted in increased student engagement and participation. Students actively participated in both online and face-to-face classes, effectively managing their assignments and activities.

Faculty members noted a heightened level of student engagement and participation, indicating the effectiveness of the hybrid learning approach in fostering active learning environments. This engagement is crucial for student success and indicates that the hybrid model effectively meets the needs of diverse learners.

Faculty 1 shared that, "The students are actively participating in the online and F2F classes and are able to accomplish their activities/assignments on given time." Faculty 2 emphasized that, "I always make sure that the students receive a consistent learning experience whether it is in person or online... employ a variety of strategies, such as interactive activities, multimedia presentations, and video presentations, to maintain student interest and participation." Faculty 6 mentioned that, "Kahit medyo challenging, nagbibigay pa rin ng paraan para maging engaging at quality ang education."

These sentiments are supported by Alsalhi et al. (2021), who emphasized the role of hybrid learning in promoting student engagement and efficiency. Additionally, Utami (2018) highlighted the benefits of hybrid learning in promoting active student engagement and self-paced learning, further underscoring the importance of student participation in hybrid learning environments.

Theme 3: Overcoming Challenges

Despite significant challenges such as power interruptions and students' lack of access to technology, educators developed innovative strategies to overcome these obstacles. This ensured continued student engagement and maintained the quality of education.

Faculty 2 shared that, "We experience a lot of challenges like power interruptions... But even with these challenges, there are still advantages to this kind of modality." Faculty 3 mentioned that, "Hindi gahol ang bata sa paggawa ng mga gawain... Kahit naka async

nakasabaybay pa din ako kung may mga tanong sa gawain. "Faculty 6 stated that, "Kahit medyo challenging, nagbibigay pa rin ng paraan para maging engaging at quality ang education."

The challenges faced by educators in hybrid learning environments, such as workload management and unfamiliarity with interactive teaching methods, align with findings from Li et al. (2023). Similarly, Suarez et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of ongoing training for faculty members to address technical issues and enhance digital competencies, highlighting the need for proactive approaches to overcome challenges in hybrid learning.

Theme 4: Positive Outcomes and Satisfaction

The hybrid learning modality yielded positive outcomes, including cost savings for students and better time management. Educators and students found this model beneficial, with some educators preferring it over traditional teaching methods.

Faculty 1 highlighted cost savings, "I believe this learning modality is also helpful for everyone because of the reduced expenses for all." Faculty 2 also noted that, "Some students also tell me that because of this hybrid modality, they can save money, as well as they are given enough time to accomplish all activities that are assigned to them." Faculty 4 considered it more effective, "I might characterize my experience as a teacher at Tanauan City College using the hybrid learning mode as a more effective method of instruction."

The positive outcomes reported by faculty members align with the findings of Alsalhi et al. (2021) and Singh et al. (2021), who highlighted the benefits of hybrid learning in promoting student efficiency and reducing financial burdens. Moreover, Mayer (2023) emphasized the importance of considering both students' and educators' perspectives in hybrid education, further underscoring the satisfaction reported by faculty members in this study.

Challenges Encountered by Faculty Members in a Hybrid Learning Environment

Theme 1: Resource Constraints

Faculty members identified resource constraints as a significant challenge within the hybrid learning environment. They highlighted the scarcity of resources, particularly in physical classroom spaces and online provision, exacerbating disparities among students. There are some, however, who proposed that resource deficits could be addressed through innovative solutions, emphasizing the role of effective communication methods in bridging the gap.

Faculty 1 expressed concern about resource scarcity, stating, "Siguro resources-- kasi Pag Face To Face kulang sa room-- Pag Online naman-- hindi maprovide ang iba lalo na ang students dahil hindi naman lahat ay may kaya talaga." Faculty 2 acknowledged the challenge but proposed solutions, affirming, "Pero tingin ko sa lahat ng challenges na meron ang Hybrid ay kaya namang solusyonan-walang resources even ang bata pwede namang magprovide."

Alsalhi et al. (2021) found that hybrid learning helps students achieve academically by ensuring thorough comprehension of course material. This aligns with the beneficial aspects of blended learning, such as adaptability, promotion of students' efficiency, and fulfillment of students' needs. However, Raes et al. (2019) note that instructors must drastically alter their teaching methods to offer a comparable high-quality educational experience for both in-person and online students, posing a significant difficulty. Educators' perceptions of hybrid education can also diverge from those of students, with educators primarily perceiving it as complex (Mayer, 2023). Thus, addressing resource constraints becomes imperative to maintain educational excellence in hybrid learning environments.

Theme 2: Technological Limitations

Technological limitations were highlighted as a major obstacle in hybrid learning. The critical issue of internet stability, where unreliable connections hindered students' participation and engagement. Additionally, concerns about students' inability to join classes due to poor internet access and the subsequent impact on learning outcomes. These findings underscore the urgent need for robust technological infrastructure to support hybrid learning initiatives.

Faculty 3 underscored the importance of internet stability, stating, "Internet stability...kapag sinabi ng bata na mahina ang net, Wala na tayong magawa..it's either totoo or Hindi ang sinasabi nila."

Furthermore, Faculty 5 highlighted the detrimental impact of internet access issues on student attendance and participation, stating, "The biggest issue I have with the hybrid learning modality is that students can't use a connection to join my class."

Singh et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of developing suitable infrastructure for hybrid and blended learning approaches to offer meaningful and captivating learning opportunities for students. However, Li et al. (2023) highlight that some students exhibit lower levels of motivation, engagement, and interaction in hybrid classes, indicating difficulties associated with hybrid learning and teaching. Hence, addressing technological limitations is crucial to ensure equitable access to education and enhance student engagement in hybrid learning environments.

Theme 3: Time Management and Curriculum Coverage

Faculty members highlighted challenges related to time management and curriculum coverage within the hybrid learning environment.

They identified that limited discussion time during online sessions as a key challenge, hindering the comprehensive coverage of syllabus discussions. Such findings underscore the importance of effective time management strategies and flexible curriculum delivery methods in optimizing hybrid learning experiences.

Faculty 7 articulated the challenge of limited discussion time, stating, "The greatest challenge I encountered in delivering the hybrid courses is the limited time in the discussion during the online/asynchronous session... To solve these challenges, I conducted extended time in the discussion during online class."

Furthermore, Faculty 6 shared insights into student engagement and participation, noting, "Nakaka- encounter ako ng mga batang sama-sama sa online class pero at the end of the day wala namang natapos buong semestre."

Suarez et al. (2020) stress the importance of ongoing training for teaching staff to bolster their digital competencies and effectively implement hybrid learning strategies. Moreover, Utami (2018) highlights that hybrid learning promotes active student engagement and aligns with student-centered learning principles. Therefore, addressing time management challenges and ensuring comprehensive curriculum coverage are crucial for enhancing educational excellence in hybrid learning environments.

Perceptions of Instructional Effectiveness in Hybrid Learning Modality

Theme 1: Pedagogical Adaptation and Efficacy

Faculty members demonstrated varying degrees of confidence in the effectiveness of their instructional strategies within the hybrid learning modality. While some rely on quantitative measures like passing rates, others prioritize qualitative indicators such as critical thinking development. This diversity of perspectives suggests the need for a multifaceted approach to assessing and enhancing instructional efficacy in hybrid learning settings.

Faculty 1 stated that, "Tingin ko naman effective ang instructional materials na ginagamit ko-- thru the use of evaluation. The fact na pumapasa ang mga students sa quizzes and performance task. Effective sya." Faculty 5 mentioned that, "I can confidently assert that the hybrid learning modality is effective based on the outcome in student performance. This unique blend of face-to-face and online instruction at Tanauan City College has indeed challenged me to reassess traditional teaching methods and adopt innovative approaches to engage students in diverse learning environments."

Faculty 7 asserted that, "I consistently monitor the impact of my instructional strategies on student learning outcomes. I ensure that I always check the output of the students to guarantee that they are not only meeting learning objectives but also developing critical thinking skills and deepening their understanding of the subject matter."

The efficacy of hybrid learning has been supported by several studies. Alsalhi et al. (2021) found that hybrid learning enhances academic achievement by ensuring a thorough comprehension of course material. This is attributed to the adaptability, promotion of efficiency, fulfillment of needs, and engagement that blended learning provides. Mayer (2023) highlighted a divergence in perspectives, noting that while students appreciate the flexibility, educators find it complex with fewer apparent advantages.

Theme 2: Overcoming Technological Barriers

Faculty members acknowledge the challenges posed by technological limitations in the hybrid learning environment and share strategies to address them effectively. Despite these barriers, they strive to ensure that students have access to resources and opportunities for meaningful engagement.

Faculty 3 mentioned, "Despite difficulties with student cooperation, I implement various engagement activities such as screen sharing and live streaming to accommodate those with internet connectivity issues." Faculty 4 stated, "Overcoming technological challenges requires creative solutions. I record online sessions for students with connectivity problems and conduct interactive recitations to ensure active participation." Faculty 5 mentioned, "Technological barriers, such as poor internet access, hinder student attendance and participation. To address this, I make recorded sessions available and encourage students to engage in discussions both online and face-to-face."

Raes et al. (2019) emphasized the need for instructors to drastically alter their teaching methods to provide a high-quality educational experience for both in-person and online students. Li et al. (2023) highlighted the increased workload for class preparation and the difficulties in designing interactive methods and effectively monitoring online students' progress. Singh et al. (2021) stressed the importance of developing suitable infrastructure and enhancing faculty capabilities in online teaching techniques to address these challenges.

Theme 3: Facilitating Interactive Learning Experiences

Faculty members emphasize the importance of fostering interactive learning experiences to enhance student engagement and participation in the hybrid learning environment. They employ various strategies and technologies to create dynamic and collaborative learning opportunities for students. Faculty 4 mentioned, "To ensure active participation, I record online sessions for students who may have connectivity issues. Additionally, I conduct online recitations where every student gets a chance to contribute and interact." Faculty 5 stated, "The hybrid model has challenged me to rethink traditional teaching methods. I focus on creating engaging

presentations and discussions, encouraging all students to share their thoughts and ideas.” Faculty 7 stipulated, “I prioritize inclusive discussions during recitations and forums to allow students to express their learning. By monitoring their output and encouraging critical thinking, I aim to deepen their understanding of the subject matter.”

The importance of interactive learning experiences in hybrid settings is well-documented. Alsalhi et al. (2021) highlighted the engagement benefits of hybrid learning, while Utami (2018) noted that this modality promotes active student engagement and self-paced learning. Suarez et al. (2020) emphasized the necessity of ongoing training for teaching staff to bolster their digital competencies, enabling them to effectively implement hybrid learning strategies and maintain educational excellence. These studies reinforce the need for diverse and interactive approaches to foster student engagement and participation in hybrid learning environments.

Strategies and Mechanisms that Faculty Members Employ to Adapt and Succeed in the Hybrid Learning Modality

Theme 1: Need for Training and Seminars

Several faculty members expressed the need for training and seminars to better equip teachers for hybrid learning. The need for professional development is crucial, especially for those who are not technologically inclined or ready.

Faculty 1 emphasized, "Sa part na to need ng seminars lalo na ang gagamit ng hybrid-- kasi hindi lahat ng teacher ay well-equipped. Maraming factors dyan-- pwedeng hindi technologically inclined si teacher, pwede namang hindi pa ready si Teacher--- so need talaga ng seminar para ipatupad ito." Faculty 4 highlighted the importance of teachers learning new tools, "Ang unang kailangang matuto dito ay mga guro. Hanggat maari ay gumagamit ako ng ibang apps/platforms para mas mapadali ang pagtuturo."

Chan, Roy & Bista, Krishna & Allen, Ryan (2021) argue that effective professional development for hybrid learning must address not just technical skills but also pedagogical approaches for online and in-person components. Moreover, Garzon, J. & Garzon, Julius (2023) found that professional development programs significantly improve teachers' self-efficacy and confidence in using technology for blended learning (a similar concept to hybrid learning).

Theme 2: Adaptation and Skill Development

Faculty members have been proactive in adapting to new technologies and developing their skills to effectively implement hybrid learning. This includes attending training sessions, utilizing new tools, and sharing knowledge with students.

Faculty 2 mentioned, "I attended several trainings related to teaching strategies using new technology. Di man ganun kahusay ay nakakasabay naman ako."

Faculty 3 noted the importance of being resourceful, "What more important now is that at least we have proper knowledge in terms of technology. Being more resourceful and keeping updated."

Faculty 6 shared their proficiency in using various technological tools, "I try to keep my skill level and adaptability in terms of technology readiness high. I am proficient at using learning management systems (LMS) like Moodle and video conferencing apps like Zoom or Google Meet to organize lessons, interact with students, and effectively handle course materials."

According to Bates (2019), effective use of technology in education can lead to improved student engagement, deeper learning, and personalized learning experiences. By developing their skills, faculty members can potentially achieve these benefits in their hybrid classrooms. Furthermore, Chauhan (2017) highlighted the positive impact of teacher professional development on student learning outcomes in technology-integrated environments.

Theme 3: Sharing Knowledge and Collaboration

Some faculty members focus on sharing their technological learnings and experiences with their students, fostering a collaborative learning environment where both teachers and students grow together.

Faculty 5 stated, "Kapag may mga natutunan ako ay palagi ko itong ibinabahagi sa mag-aaral at tinatanong ko sila sa experience ng paggamit nito." Faculty 7 emphasized the continuous development and sharing of technological skills, "Despite these challenges, I remain committed by continuously refining my technological skills, troubleshooting issues as they arise, and seeking innovative solutions, to ensure that students will also be technology inclined individuals."

Alkhalwaldeh, M. A., & Khasawneh, M. A. S. (2023) research on online communities and collaborative platforms in hybrid learning. Their study investigates the effectiveness of online communities and collaborative platforms in fostering knowledge sharing and professional development among teachers, specifically within hybrid learning contexts. Their findings highlight the benefits of these platforms in facilitating discussions, sharing best practices, and troubleshooting challenges related to hybrid learning implementation.

Theme 4: Enhancing Student Engagement through Technology

Faculty members have creatively integrated various technological tools to enhance student engagement and learning experiences in hybrid settings. This includes using virtual whiteboards, videos, simulations, and interactive modules to cater to diverse learning styles.

Faculty 3 shared, "We were able to design new virtual learning tools that were more effective and entertaining for our students, as well as modify some of our previous lessons for the online setting." Faculty 6 mentioned, "By incorporating videos, simulations, and interactive modules into my lessons, I can cater to diverse learning styles and enhance comprehension and retention."

Chauhan's (2017) meta-analysis supports this approach, indicating that when technology is comprehensively integrated into pedagogy, it acts as a powerful tool for effective learning among elementary students. The results confirmed that technology has a medium effect on learning effectiveness among students. This aligns with the faculty's use of technology to enhance student engagement and learning experiences, emphasizing the importance of integrating technology into teaching practices to cater to diverse learning styles and enhance student comprehension and retention.

Faculty Members' Insights and Recommendations for Enhancing the Effectiveness of the Hybrid Learning Modality at Tanauan City College

Theme 1: Accessibility and Infrastructure

Faculty members emphasized the importance of ensuring accessibility and robust infrastructure to support hybrid learning. This includes strong internet connections, reliable access to technology, effective monitoring, and improvements in the learning management system (LMS). Faculty 1 stated, "Accessibility siguro ng lahat --- both teachers and students. Then monitoring talaga ng school na -- both students and teachers ay gumagawa nito or nagpaparticipate dito."

Additionally, Faculty 1 suggested, "Siguro mas maganda kung nagkakaroon ng system ang school na pwede nilang makita ang grade nila as individual. Yung may portal sila. Then sa LMS naman hindi limited ang capacity na pwedeng mag-upload ng mga videos and lahat ng pwedeng magamit sa Teaching and Learning scenarios."

Faculty 3 highlighted the need for strong internet connections, "Extensive training for teachers as well as to students in terms of modern technology and hybrid learning. Availability of strong internet connection within the campus." Faculty 7 recommended improving bandwidth, "I think there is a need to improve our bandwidth or internet capacity so that the students and faculty members could upload their accomplished work without the risk of rejection from the school server."

The importance of robust infrastructure and accessibility is supported by findings from Li et al. (2023), who emphasized the need for reliable technology and internet access in hybrid learning environments. Suarez et al. (2020) also highlighted the necessity of technical support and infrastructure improvements to ensure seamless hybrid learning experiences.

Theme 2: Continuous Professional Development

The necessity of ongoing professional development for faculty members was a common theme. Faculty emphasized the importance of continuous learning and self-improvement to stay updated with technological advancements and teaching strategies in a hybrid learning environment. Faculty 2 mentioned, "Continuous learning, self-growth, and development.. dapat kahit may mga trainings na.. tuloy tuloy pa rin ang pag papaunlad sa sarili." Faculty 4 stressed continual opportunities for professional development, "To give academic staff members continual opportunities for professional development to assist them in acquiring the abilities and know-how required to instruct in a hybrid learning environment."

Faculty 7 recommended comprehensive professional development programs, "Tanauan City Colleges should organize comprehensive professional development programs and workshops to enhance educators' technological skills and strategies for hybrid teaching." Faculty 7 also suggested, "I would like to recommend for the improvement of our MIS facilities first and maybe additional manpower for this office also to help our students and faculty members. Furthermore, I would like to recommend to have a regular (maybe every beginning of the semester) to have development seminars/training for the faculty members regarding the Learning Management System."

Continuous professional development is crucial for adapting to hybrid learning environments. This is supported by Alsalhi et al. (2021), who emphasized the need for ongoing training to enhance faculty members' digital competencies. Mayer (2023) also highlighted the importance of continuous professional development to improve teaching effectiveness in hybrid learning settings.

Theme 3: Blended Learning Approaches

Faculty members discussed the importance of blending face-to-face (F2F) and online learning, particularly for subjects that require hands-on experiences. They suggested that students should have options to choose their preferred mode of learning. Faculty 5 stated, "Idagdag sana sa hybrid ang F2F dahil may mga subjects na hindi talaga pwedeng naka online class lamang. Sana magkaroon din ang bata ng option kung gusto nila ng hybrid." Faculty 7 recommended maximizing online class periods, "The only thing I would like to recommend is to use the entire period of time of each course in the online class. Let's not limit it to one hour or one and a half hours during the week of the supposed to be a non-F2F class."

Blended learning approaches are essential for subjects that require practical and hands-on experiences. This aligns with findings from Raes et al. (2019), who emphasized the benefits of hybrid learning in providing a balance between online and face-to-face interactions. Utami (2018) also highlighted the importance of offering flexible learning options to cater to students' diverse needs.

Theme 4: Effective Use and Improvement of LMS

Faculty members underscored the need for effective use and continuous improvement of the learning management system (LMS). They highlighted the importance of user-friendly design, comprehensive training, and regular updates to meet the evolving needs of hybrid learning.

Faculty 2 emphasized the importance of exploring the LMS, "I explore ang LMS. Magsiyasat at gumugol ng panahon para dito." Faculty 3 stressed accessibility and mandate, "Have an LMS that is easily accessible to all teachers and students. Mandate to all students as well as all teachers the use of LMS." Faculty 4 suggested optimizing the LMS, "Utilize less resources to accomplish more. Following my experience with our institution's virtual learning environment, these are my suggestions for making the LMS as effective as possible for teaching. You must EVALUATE your present and future LMS requirements before you can begin to optimize your LMS." Faculty 5 expressed dissatisfaction with the current LMS, "Hindi po ako natutuwa sa Moodle. Sobrang hassle. Pati mga bata ay nahihirapang gumamit. Iimprove or palitan ito."

Faculty 6 highlighted the potential of a user-friendly LMS, "For LMS they must always ensure user-friendly design. LMS can serve as a powerful platform for delivering engaging, interactive, and personalized learning experiences." Faculty 7 recommended regular training and budget allocation, "Maybe, we can recommend for the earmarking of budget from the LGU/School Board for a more advanced and user-friendly LMS."

The importance of an effective LMS is supported by Li et al. (2023), who emphasized the need for user-friendly and comprehensive LMS platforms to support hybrid learning. Suarez et al. (2020) also highlighted the role of continuous training and updates in optimizing the use of LMS in educational institutions.

Lived Experiences of the Students on the Hybrid Learning Modality

Theme 1: Flexibility and Convenience

Many students appreciate the hybrid learning modality for its flexibility and convenience, especially those who have additional responsibilities such as work or family. The ability to manage their schedules more effectively and save on transportation costs are significant advantages.

Student 1 highlighted the cost and time benefits, "Maganda ang hybrid dahil nakakatipid kaming mga estudyante sa pamasahe at iwas gastos, sapagkat may mga oras sa aming 'schedule' na malayo ang agwat ng oras sa isa't isa na nagko-cause ng pagkainip sa pag-aantay sa susunod na klase."

Student 2 emphasized the balance between learning and personal responsibilities, "Maganda sya sa pagkat ang madalas napasok sa ating paaralan ay mga working students at kadalasan ay ang walang kakayahang makapag-aral sa iba't ibang dahilan. Tulad kopo bilang nanay, kahit papaano maayod naman po ako nakakapag aral at nakakagawa. Natututo na, nakakatulong pa sa bahay."

Student 5 also appreciated the ability to balance work and study, "For me po, okay sya para sa kagaya kong working student, na mamanage ko ang oras ng pag aaral at pag wowork."

The flexibility offered by hybrid learning aligns with findings from Raes et al. (2019), who noted that hybrid models provide students with the ability to balance academic and personal responsibilities more effectively. Alsalhi et al. (2021) also highlighted that the flexibility of hybrid learning is particularly beneficial for students with diverse schedules.

Theme 2: Challenges of Online Learning

While recognizing the benefits, students also identified several challenges associated with the online component of hybrid learning, such as distractions at home and the perceived lack of learning effectiveness.

Student 1 mentioned the distractions, "Maganda na mahirap ang pag-aaral ng hybrid, dahil hindi madali ang pag-aaral online sapagkat una na rito ang ingay sa paligid na nagko-cause ng distraction saamin."

Student 4 expressed concerns about the effectiveness of online learning, "Mas mainam po ang face-to-face classes, dahil minsan ay hindi nakakapag klase pag online at hindi din masyado madami natutunan pag online."

These challenges are consistent with findings from Mayer (2023), who emphasized that distractions and the effectiveness of online learning are significant concerns in hybrid education. Similarly, Utami (2018) pointed out that maintaining student engagement in online learning environments requires addressing these common challenges.

Theme 3: Enhanced Learning and Personal Growth

Some students found that hybrid learning positively impacted their personal growth and understanding of various subjects. The ability to improve knowledge and skills in a flexible learning environment was seen as a significant benefit.

Student 3 shared their positive experience, "Ang aking naging experience, Dito ay na improve ko Ang aking kaalaman tungkol sa mga

bagay-bagay." Student 6 found hybrid learning beneficial for time management, "Mas maayos po kasi gawa po nang hindi po ako nahihirapan sa oras."

The potential for personal growth in hybrid learning settings is supported by Alsalhi et al. (2021), who found that hybrid learning environments can enhance students' knowledge and skills by providing diverse and flexible learning opportunities. Mayer (2023) also noted that hybrid learning can foster personal development by accommodating different learning paces and styles.

Theme 4: Support for Working and Non-Traditional Students

The hybrid learning model is particularly beneficial for working students and those with non-traditional study schedules. The ability to juggle work and study commitments more effectively is a crucial aspect of hybrid learning. Student 2 highlighted this support, "Nasa adult naman kung paano nya i aadopt at accept pero saakin po so far ay maayos at nakakatulong. Natututo na, nakakatulong pa sa bahay."

Student 4 appreciated the balance between work, study, and rest, "Because the hybrid in TCC allowed me to devote more time to work and my studies while also allowing me to rest, I am grateful that I can now support myself."

Supporting working and non-traditional students through hybrid learning is a theme echoed by Raes et al. (2019), who found that hybrid models can provide the flexibility needed to accommodate students' diverse life commitments. Alsalhi et al. (2021) also noted that hybrid learning can help reduce the educational barriers faced by working students, making higher education more

Specific Challenges Students Encounter within the Hybrid Learning Modality

Theme 1: Technical Issues and Connectivity Problems

Technical difficulties, such as poor internet connections and device malfunctions, significantly hinder the hybrid learning experience. These issues disrupt the learning process and reduce students' ability to participate fully in online classes.

Student 1 highlighted the impact of technical issues, "Some challenges faced in hybrid learning courses include difficulties in time management, limited interaction with peers and instructors, technical issues, and distractions at home." Student 4 mentioned slow internet connections, "Only when it is online, sometimes my connection is slow and not able to attend the session smoothly." Student 5 emphasized the prevalence of technical issues, "A lot of students are experiencing challenges when it comes to hybrid learning courses. One is that students have mobile technical issues and a low internet connection." Student 7 discussed the impact of lacking WiFi, "Malaki yung epekto dahil wala kaming WiFi at minsan sa sobrang pagod sa work at di nakaka attend kahit online class dahil nakakatulog."

Research by Agormedah et al. (2020) and Almahasees et al. (2021) similarly highlights how technical issues, particularly with internet connectivity, are common obstacles in hybrid learning environments. These issues can detract from students' engagement and academic performance, necessitating robust technological support and infrastructure.

Theme 2: Time Management and Stress

Balancing academic responsibilities with other personal or professional commitments is a significant challenge in hybrid learning. Students often struggle with managing their time effectively, leading to increased stress and potential burnout.

Student 2 discussed the need for agility and responsibility, "Minamabuti ko pa ding maging positive sa lahat ng bagay, isantabi at kalimutan ang mga makaka-apekto sa pag-punta ko sa aking tagumpay."

Student 3 mentioned distractions at home, "Tulad nalang ng mga ingay, at iba't ibang oangyayare sa loob mg bagay ja hindi mo inaasahan. Hindi madalas nakakafocus sa aralin."

Student 7 emphasized the effects of fatigue, "Minsan sa sobrang pagod sa work at di nakaka attend kahit online class dahil nakakatulog."

Research by Adnan and Anwar (2020) and Gonzalez et al. (2020) supports these findings, indicating that time management and stress are significant factors affecting students' ability to succeed in hybrid learning. Effective time management strategies and mental health support are crucial in mitigating these challenges.

Theme 3: Limited Interaction and Engagement

The hybrid learning model often leads to reduced interaction between students and faculty, as well as among peers. This lack of engagement can hinder the learning experience and decrease motivation.

Student 1 noted the limited interaction, "Limited interaction with peers and instructors, technical issues, and distractions at home."

Student 5 highlighted the decrease in engagement, "A lot of students at Tanauan City College said that having hybrid learning courses caused the least engagement with their classmates and teachers due to the online class."

Student 6 suggested strategies to improve engagement, "Implementing strategies such as offering clear communication, providing

technical assistance, organizing orientation sessions, and creating a supportive learning environment can greatly aid students in adapting to the changes."

According to Martin and Bolliger (2018) and Banna et al. (2015), fostering interaction and engagement in hybrid learning environments is crucial for enhancing students' educational experiences. Active learning strategies, regular feedback, and community-building activities can help address these issues.

Theme 4: Adaptation to Hybrid Learning

Adapting to the hybrid learning model, which involves transitioning between online and offline environments, poses a challenge for many students. The need for clear communication and support during this transition is essential.

Student 6 mentioned the difficulties of adapting, "Some students are having a hard time adapting to the transition between online and offline classroom environments."

Student 7 also highlighted the confusion about schedules, "Minsan nakaka apekto yung linggo na akala ko ay may ftf pero online pala."

Research by Hodges et al. (2020) and Means et al. (2014) indicates that adaptation challenges are common in hybrid learning. Providing clear guidance, orientation sessions, and continuous support can help students navigate the complexities of hybrid education more effectively.

Aspects of the Hybrid Learning Modality that the Students Find Most Engaging

Theme 1: Flexibility and Time Management

The hybrid learning model provides flexibility, enabling students to manage their studies alongside work or other commitments. This aspect is particularly beneficial for working students.

Student 3 explained: "Yung Sistema ng paghahatihatid ng mga oras ng klase upang makapag working student ang mga magaaral na walang sapat na pera."

Student 6 added: "Since may work/business po ako, madalas ko po nama-manage yung time ko when it comes sa pag aaral and business ko po, and dahil walang problema po don, nafi-feel ko po yung effectiveness"

Theme 2: Preference for Face-to-Face Learning

Some students prefer face-to-face (f-to-f) learning for its clarity and effective delivery of topics. They believe that in-person instruction enhances their understanding and learning experience. Student 4 stated: "f-to-f po, para mas klaro ang pagtuturo." Student 5 agreed: "f-to-f, dahil malinaw ang way ng pag aaral, na dedeliver na ayos ang topic."

Theme 3: Independent Learning and Habit Formation

Hybrid learning fosters independent learning and the development of effective study habits. This approach helps students balance their academic responsibilities with other aspects of their lives.

Student 7 reflected: "Studying independently and acquiring the necessary learning habits to support my studies, as well as enabling me to do my work at the same time, were all made possible by hybrid learning."

Student 2 shared: "With hybrid learning, I have learned to manage my time better and become more disciplined. The flexibility of hybrid classes allows me to plan my study schedule around my other commitments, which has improved my overall productivity."

Student 1 added: "Hybrid learning has taught me to be more self-reliant. Without the constant presence of a teacher, I had to develop my research skills and find resources on my own, which has been invaluable in enhancing my understanding of the subjects."

Strategies and Mechanisms that Students Employ to Adapt and Succeed in the Hybrid Learning Modality

Theme 1: Flexibility and Time Management

Students highlighted the importance of flexibility in managing their academic and personal responsibilities. The hybrid learning modality provided opportunities to balance studies with other commitments, such as work and family duties, thus fostering effective time management skills.

Student 2 noted, "Ito po ay nakakatulong lalo't higit sa nais makatapos na kapos at kinakailangan magtrabaho, hindi lang iyon sa kagaya ko din nanay na kailangan ng anak dahil bata pa. Nakakasali at nakakakilos ng malaya. Sumatotal ang mga online class at pagbibigay ng aktibidades ay malayang naihayag na ipapasa sa mas madaling paraan."

This statement emphasizes the flexibility offered by hybrid learning, which is especially beneficial for working students and parents.

Student 4 shared, "Ayun nga po, the reason why satisfied po ako sa current learning modality is because of my business, before po ako umattend sa class, natatapos ko na po yung mga need tapusin sa business po namin."

This illustrates how students leverage hybrid learning to effectively manage and prioritize their business responsibilities alongside academic commitments. Student 5 added, "Flexible - having both online and in-person classes helps me better organize my time so that I can attend to other obligations or responsibilities outside of school."

The flexibility of hybrid learning enables students to develop robust time management skills, balancing academic and personal responsibilities effectively. These insights align with Alsalhi et al. (2021), who emphasized that hybrid learning promotes adaptability and efficiency, and with Singh et al. (2021), who noted the importance of infrastructure development to support such flexible learning environments.

Theme 2: Accessibility and Convenience

Hybrid learning has increased accessibility and convenience for students, allowing them to participate in classes and complete assignments more efficiently.

Student 2 emphasized, "Nakakasali at nakakakilos ng malaya. Sumatotal ang mga online class at pagbibigay ng aktibidades ay malayang naihayag na ipapasa sa mas madaling paraan."

This highlights the convenience of online classes and the ease of submitting assignments digitally. Student 3 stated, "Ngayong online class paden mas pabor saken Dahil kapag F2F ay mashindi ko maintindihan Ang mga tinoturo." This suggests that some students find online classes more comprehensible and accessible than face-to-face sessions. These perspectives resonate with Utami (2018), who highlighted that hybrid learning promotes active student engagement and self-paced learning, making education more accessible and convenient for diverse learners.

Theme 3: Adaptation to Changing Learning Environments

Students have developed strategies to adapt to the constant shifts between online and face-to-face learning due to external factors like school renovations. These strategies include adjusting to new learning environments and maintaining academic performance despite challenges.

Student 1 shared, "Today, it is slightly harder to study fully online. It seems like we are experiencing a pandemic again. From online to FtF to online again, the adjustments are there—attending class while doing chores at home. I understand the constant shifts because of school renovations. But it is hard for us, the students, to adjust ourselves again for the next semester."

This statement underscores the challenges students face in adapting to hybrid learning and the strategies they employ to manage these changes effectively.

Student 5 also noted, "For Personal Growth - This can entail resolving issues with online learning environments, enhancing time management abilities, or developing effective communication skills in a variety of media."

The development of personal growth strategies highlights how students adapt to hybrid learning environments, overcoming challenges and enhancing their skills. These challenges and adaptations align with findings from Li et al. (2023) and Suarez et al. (2020), who emphasized the need for ongoing support and training for both students and educators to navigate the complexities of hybrid learning effectively.

Theme 4: Satisfaction and Personal Growth

Despite the challenges, students expressed satisfaction with the hybrid learning modality, highlighting personal growth and improved time management skills as significant benefits.

Student 4 mentioned, "Ayun nga po, the reason why satisfied po ako sa current learning modality is because of my business, before po ako umattend sa class, natatapos ko na po yung mga need tapusin sa business po namin."

Student 5 added, "I can give a thorough and convincing explanation of why I am happy with Tanauan City College's present hybrid schedule learning modality by including particular examples or occurrences that highlight these aspects."

These statements reflect students' satisfaction with hybrid learning, which supports their personal growth and allows them to manage various responsibilities effectively. The positive outcomes reported by students align with the findings of Alsalhi et al. (2021) and Singh et al. (2021), who highlighted the benefits of hybrid learning in promoting student efficiency and reducing financial burdens. Moreover, Mayer (2023) emphasized the importance of considering both students' and educators' perspectives in hybrid education, further underscoring the satisfaction reported by students in this study.

Students' Insights and Recommendations for Enhancing the Effectiveness of the Hybrid Learning Modality at Tanauan City College

Theme 1: Enhancing Student Engagement and Interaction

Students emphasized the need for more interactive online platforms and regular communication to enhance engagement and interaction

in the hybrid learning environment.

Student 1 suggested, "Enhancing hybrid learning, integrate interactive online platforms for engagement, offer flexible scheduling, provide diverse learning resources, maintain regular communication, and personalize learning paths. These improvements aim to boost the student's engagement, flexibility, collaboration, and support, enriching the overall learning experience for students in hybrid education."

This recommendation highlights the importance of utilizing technology to create a more engaging and supportive learning environment, which aligns with findings from Alsalhi et al. (2021) who emphasized the role of hybrid learning in promoting student engagement.

Student 2 noted, "Sa aking palagay ay kinakailangang maayos at sariling online application na educational na dun na makikita lahat ng announcement para aware din sila. Ayos din ang google classroom set up na nag uupdate palagi upang aware ang students higitan ang ganun dahil napakaayos na ng hybrid kailangan maging active din sila sa ganung paraan para makacomply."

This recommendation points to the need for a dedicated online platform to centralize information and ensure students are kept up-to-date, which can significantly improve student engagement and compliance.

These insights echo Utami (2018), who emphasized the benefits of hybrid learning in promoting active student engagement and self-paced learning, making education more interactive and responsive to students' needs.

Theme 2: Addressing Students' Socio-Economic Status

A critical recommendation was to understand and address the socio-economic challenges faced by students to prevent disruptions in their education.

Student 3 recommended, "Alamin muna nila Ang estado ng buhay ng mga estudyante upang may magawa silang paraan para Hindi ito tumigil sa pag-aaral."

This suggests that educational institutions should assess students' living conditions and provide necessary support to ensure continuous learning, a sentiment supported by Raes et al. (2019) and Mayer (2023), who emphasized the need for institutions to consider students' diverse backgrounds and needs in hybrid education.

Theme 3: Maintaining and Improving Quality of Teaching

Some students expressed satisfaction with the current hybrid learning modality but emphasized the importance of maintaining the quality of teaching.

Student 4 stated, "For me, okay na po ako sa learning modality na to and wala na po akong maisa- suggest dahil maganda parin po ang quality ng teaching even though online class and satisfied na po ako. Thank you po."

This reflects a positive perception of the hybrid learning modality, highlighting the importance of sustaining high-quality teaching practices, which aligns with findings from Singh et al. (2021), who noted the need for ongoing support and development of faculty members to maintain educational excellence.

Theme 4: Providing Adequate Time for Learning

A key recommendation was to allocate sufficient time for each subject, especially to accommodate slow learners, ensuring that lessons are fully understood.

Student 5 suggested, "To provide enough time so that each subject can concentrate more on its lessons. Slow learners will benefit from it since the teacher will have enough time to fully and accurately convey the teachings to the class."

This underscores the need for flexible scheduling to cater to the diverse learning paces of students, a point also highlighted by Alsalhi et al. (2021) who emphasized the role of hybrid learning in addressing individual differences among students.

Theme 5: Utilizing Technology and Online Applications

Students recommended the integration of specific online applications to streamline educational processes and enhance learning experiences.

Student 2 mentioned, "Kinakailangang maayos at sariling online application na educational na dun na makikita lahat ng announcement para aware din sila."

This suggests that having a dedicated and well-organized online platform could significantly improve the hybrid learning experience by centralizing information and facilitating better communication between students and faculty.

These recommendations align with the insights from Suarez et al. (2020), who highlighted the importance of suitable infrastructure and digital competency training for faculty members to support effective hybrid learning.

Conclusions

The research highlights the multifaceted experiences of students and faculty members within the hybrid learning modality, underscoring both the benefits and challenges.

Hybrid learning at Tanauan City College has fostered greater flexibility, enabling students to balance academic and personal responsibilities, and has encouraged faculty to develop more adaptive and innovative teaching methods. However, the study also reveals significant challenges, such as resource constraints, technological limitations, and the need for effective time management and curriculum coverage. Despite these hurdles, both students and faculty members express overall satisfaction with the hybrid learning model, appreciating its potential to cater to diverse learning needs and promote personal and academic growth.

In light of the findings, several strategic recommendations are proposed to enhance the educational experience for both faculty members and students. Firstly, it is essential to provide regular and comprehensive training sessions for faculty members to improve their digital literacy and teaching strategies, focusing on e-learning tools, interactive teaching methods, and effective online student engagement techniques. Investment in robust technological infrastructure, including reliable internet connections and user-friendly learning management systems (LMS), is crucial, along with providing necessary technological resources and support to ensure equitable access to hybrid learning for all.

To enhance student engagement and participation, interactive online platforms and multimedia resources should be integrated, offering diverse learning activities that cater to different learning styles and needs.

Addressing the socio-economic challenges faced by students by providing financial support, affordable access to technology, and flexible learning schedules is also vital. Creating a dedicated online portal for centralized access to academic resources, announcements, and course materials will further support students.

Offering options for students to choose between online, face-to-face, or hybrid modes of learning based on their preferences and needs while ensuring hands-on subjects have sufficient face-to-face components will facilitate practical learning experiences.

Finally, establishing mechanisms for regular feedback from students and faculty to continuously improve the hybrid learning model, along with monitoring academic outcomes and engagement levels, will help identify areas for improvement and implement timely interventions. By implementing these recommendations, Tanauan City College can optimize its hybrid learning modality, ensuring a more inclusive, engaging, and effective educational environment that meets the evolving needs of its academic community.

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